

ANALYSIS OF THE LEVEL OF LEARNING OF OPTICAL COMMUNICATION NETWORK MANAGEMENT METHODS ON A GLOBAL SCALE

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Introduction.

In the following decades, various info-communication systems based on the combined use of telecommunications and computer technology are entering various aspects of human activity (government, politics, defense, economy, finance, medicine, etc.) and remain a vital necessity for them. In the infocommunication system, compared to traditional telephony, the requirements for reliability and transmission quality are increasing sharply. Based on this, the unreliability (rejections) of telecommunication means leads to a significant increase in user losses, which increases the requirements for telecommunication reliability.

The modern era brings the process of informatization of the society to a sharp development. This process encourages users of information and communication services to connect to telecommunications networks with high speed (broadband). This demand is due to the rapid growth of Internet users and the introduction of multimedia, video conferencing, electronic digital signature, electronic commerce, electronic document circulation and other modern services.

It is known that in order to increase the volume, speed and quality of information flow, there should be a routing environment with a high level of throughput for receiving information. There are currently no competing means of optical communication that meet the above-mentioned requirements. In addition, it is possible to transmit a large amount of information over any distance through optical means of communication. Therefore, optical communication is an excellent and promising means of communication that develops information communication technologies of the society.

Optical communication based on optoelectronics, that is, all-optical networks AON (All-optical Networks) is the future of telecommunication networks. The all-optical connection covers the backbone networks, as well as the subscribers' network connection, and provides broadband connections to the telecommunications networks of the customers. In all-optical communication, switching, multiplexing and regeneration are performed only on the basis of optical technology, not optoelectronic or electro-optical. In this case, the

technical and economic indicators of the device, efficiency and quality of transmission speed will increase several times. Optical switches, optical regenerators, amplifiers, filters, and spectrum intensification systems are used in the application of photon technology to communication systems.

In our republic, a lot of work has been done in the field of informatization of society, development of telecommunication networks, and these works are still ongoing. For this purpose, in the past years, the construction of the national segment of the TOO (Trans-Asia-Europe) highway, a digital transport network that meets world standards, has been started, and a fiber optic communication line of over 830 km has been put into use. Fiber optic cables from the German company Siemens were used in the national segment. Currently, optical fiber cables with various functions and structures are being produced for communication and telecommunication systems. New types of single-mode cables are being produced for broadband long-distance communication systems, including optical fiber for trunk communication. High requirements are also placed on the attenuation and dispersion indicators of optical fiber during information transmission in trunk communication lines. In addition, optical fibers that ensure the preservation of the polarization of optical radiation are also being produced. The development of such cables used in trunk communication is complicated and expensive. When such cables are used, laser transmitters are used. High requirements are placed on laser transmitters, the purity of the radiation spectrum, and the stability of radiation images.

In systems with a speed of up to 100 Mbit/s and limited communication distance, it is better to use multimode optical cables, which are relatively inexpensive and easily compatible with end devices. As a wave source, it is possible to use simple semiconductor light-emitting diodes irradiating in many modes. The creation of new types of optical fibers, broadband quantum optical amplifiers makes it possible to build a complete optical system and optical tracts. Such information transmission technologies are used to create systems with a transmission range of 100 and 1000 Gbit/s.

Although this optical connection has several advantages, it also has disadvantages. This is explained by the high cost of optical communication devices and the imperfection of some optical communication technologies. Due to this, the following disadvantages can be cited:

- the cost of element base of optical communication systems. Economical cost of optical transmitters and receivers. Especially the high cost of optical generators (laser) radiation sources and their limited service life. Also, production of passive optical devices (attenuator, switch, multiplexer, etc.) in optical communication systems leads to high costs;
- complexity of installation and maintenance of fiber optic communication lines. Compared to electric cable systems, the complexity of construction of optical cable systems, their technical use, measurement and installation work requires high skills;
- the need for special fiber protection. In order to avoid loss of signals in microslit bands, the fiber must be protected from overloading and bending. Organization of special protection. In order to increase the level of reliability, during the production of optical communication fibers,

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coating the optical fiber with a special varnish based on epoxy acrylate. Alternatively, the cable can be further strengthened due to a special steel cable and glass plastic rods.

According to information, 690 km of optical fiber communication lines were laid in Uzbekistan during 6 months of 2018. 1004 new base stations were installed. 483 of them support 3G and 4G LTE networks. Currently, the length of optical communication systems in our country has reached 24,500,000 kilometers, and the total number of base stations has reached 20,994 thousand. connection rate reached 70%.

The total number of users of mobile Internet systems in our republic has increased to 22 million. According to statistics, the number of mobile Internet users is more than 19 million. In order to develop optical communication systems, a number of mobile communication base stations were installed in our republic, and their total number increased to 26,000. This year, laying of 12,000 km of optical fiber communication lines and installation of 2,200 mobile communication base stations across the country is planned. Also, in 2019, 10,000 km long optical fiber communication lines were laid in the regions within the framework of the "Construction of optical fiber communication lines" project, and the total length of optical communication systems was more than 36,600 km.

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